

IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECT GIGO (GARBAGE IN, GARBAGE) AT MORONG NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL: AN EVALUATION

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Implementation of Project GIGO (Garbage In, Garbage) at Morong National Senior High School: An Evaluation

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Abstract

Proper waste management in school is a crucial issue to maintain a safe and conducive learning environment for all the members of the educational community. This paper aimed to evaluate the implementation of Project GIGO (Garbage In, Garbage Out) at Morong National High School-Senior High during the School Year 2022-2023. This study used quantitative descriptive research design using an online survey questionnaire which was administered to thirty (30) teachers and one hundred (100) students of MNHS-SH. Based on the results, the two groups of respondents have similar evaluation on the implementation of Project GIGO in terms of objectives, process, monitoring and evaluation, and stakeholder's participation. It is important to note that the school should improve its linkages to seek support for its implementation. In addition, some of the problems that were given by the respondents were lack of knowledge, disobedience of some students, and limitations on the materials. Meanwhile they have suggested establishing strong connections with external members of the school, intensify the monitoring and evaluation, and spread more awareness among its clientele for the success of the project.

Keywords: *proper waste management, evaluation, students, teachers*

Introduction

Schools play a vital role in shaping the future of our society, instilling knowledge, and fostering the development of young minds. However, they also generate a substantial amount of waste, which can have significant environmental and social consequences if not managed responsibly. The management of school waste has emerged as a pressing issue that demands immediate attention, as it directly impacts the health of our planet and the well-being of current and future generations.

The concept of school waste management goes beyond simply collecting and disposing of trash. It encompasses a holistic approach that involves waste reduction, recycling, reuse, and raising awareness about environmental responsibility among students, educators, and school administrators. An effective waste management system in schools not only reduces their ecological footprint but also serves as a valuable educational tool, empowering students to become environmentally conscious citizens who are equipped to tackle global sustainability challenges. This research explores the challenges faced by schools in managing solid waste effectively, examines existing waste management practices, and proposes sustainable strategies to promote a greener and more responsible learning environment.

Relatively, DepEd Order No. 5, s. 2014, the National Greening Program (NGP) implemented solid waste management rules, among other things, since one of

the essential elements for achieving the objectives of the DepEd for biodiversity conservation and the prevention and adaptation to climate change is ecological solid waste management (ESWM). Moreover, the DepEd is further obligated under RA 9003, Part 6, Rule 21, Section 2 to implement ESWM in the school systems at all levels actively, focusing the participation of school administrators, teaching and non-teaching personnel, and students in school-wide and local community waste management initiatives. The school administrators acted on this directive by including SWM techniques in the school improvement plan. However, despite the implementation of numerous plans of action and initiatives, waste management problems at schools remain unresolved.

In response to the continuous improvement of the SDO Rizal, the Garbage In Garbage Out (GIGO) as standard in maintaining quality in the workplace will be implemented in Morong National High School-Senior High which will elevate a student's attitude in the school. Clean hallways, classroom and canteen result in a lively institution which makes it conducive for learning. This Project GIGO will allow the students to know proper waste disposal wherein their trashes will not be dumped in the school, but the trashes will be dumped in their own houses. As regards to this, the researcher opted to conduct this study to evaluate the implementation of Project GIGO, assess the current state of solid waste management in schools, identify the barriers to effective waste reduction, and explore innovative strategies to create sustainable waste management systems. By promoting environmentally

responsible practices within schools, students are empowered to become environmentally conscious citizens who actively contribute to a cleaner and healthier planet.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the implementation of Project GIGO at Morong National High School-Senior High during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions.

1. How do the teachers and students evaluate the implementation of Project GIGO in terms of the following?
 - 1.1 Objectives;
 - 1.2 Process;
 - 1.3 Monitoring and Evaluation; and
 - 1.4 Stakeholder's Participation?
2. What problems do the respondents encounter during the implementation of Project GIGO?
3. What suggestions do the respondents give to further improve the implementation of Project GIGO?

Literature Review

The health, safety, and well-being of the students, teachers, and other school personnel are all protected at school by proper solid waste management (Roy et al., 2015). Through Republic Act no. 9003, SWM concepts were integrated into education (Molina, 2021). Also, Republic Act No. 8491 states that the core value "Makakalikasan" cares for the environment, utilizes resources wisely, judiciously, and economically, and includes indicator practices of waste management (Llego, 2019). Solid waste management in schools is a critical environmental issue that demands attention as educational institutions generate substantial amounts of waste daily. Proper waste management not only helps schools reduce their ecological footprint but also serves as a valuable educational tool to instill environmental consciousness among students.

Solid waste management is the collection, transport, processing, recycling, or disposal of waste materials. It is the materials produced by human activity and is generally undertaken to reduce their effect on health, aesthetics, or amenity. Waste management is also carried out to reduce the materials' effect on the environment and to recover resources from them. It can also involve solid, liquid or gaseous substances, with different methods and fields of expertise for each

essential (Marello and Helwege, 2014).

Methodology

This study used quantitative descriptive research design in analyzing the evaluation of the teachers and students on the implementation of Project GIGO. According to Siedlecki (2020), in a descriptive study, the researchers studied the variables as they appear in their natural context and no manipulation is done. This is complemented by a survey method which is useful for collecting information from a group to describe characteristics, such as opinions and attitudes, of the population of which that group is a part of. It involves the collection and analysis of data about people or materials with the intention to compare existing and required standards. Permission to conduct the study was secured. When permitted and with the guidance of the School Head, the researcher administered the questionnaire-checklist herself.

Participants of the Study

The researcher gathered the necessary and needed data for this study from the thirty (30) teachers and one hundred (100) students at Morong National High School- Senior High. They were chosen using purposive sampling technique. The teachers were chosen since they were included in the implementation of the project. As regards the students, they came from the different sections in Grade 11 and 12 at MNHS-SH. The researcher considered their willingness to participate in this study.

Instruments of the Study

The researcher used a researcher-made survey questionnaire to evaluate the implementation of Project GIGO at Morong National Senior High School. An online version using the Google Form was sent to all the respondents. She herself monitored the form to ensure accuracy and reliability of information.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher herself explained and gave the informed consent to each participant before the conduct of the study. She ensured them that the information would be used with utmost confidentiality and within the purpose of the study only.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of the respondents on the implementation of Project GIGO in terms of the cited aspects

Table 1. Evaluation of the Teachers and Students on the Implementation of Project GIGO in terms of Objectives

Objectives	Teachers		Parents	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The project provides school-based solid waste management information for all stakeholders.	3.50	Much Agree	3.33	Much Agree
2. The project equips the teachers and students with the necessary knowledge and skills in maintaining clean and safe learning environment.	3.47	Much Agree	3.61	Much Agree
3. The project instills good habits among its teachers and students about cleanliness and safety of the school.	3.70	Much Agree	3.51	Much Agree
4. The project conforms with the goals of the Department of Education on National Greening Program (NGP).	3.80	Much Agree	3.50	Much Agree
5. The project addresses existing problems as regards to garbage in keeping the learning space conducive to teaching-learning spectrums.	3.50	Much Agree	3.31	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.59	Much Agree	3.45	Much Agree

It can be seen on the table that the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the implementation of Project GIGO in terms of objectives gained an overall mean of 3.59 and 3.45 respectively and both verbally interpreted as Much Agree. This infers that the teachers and students considerably believe that the aims of Project GIGO are aligned to the target of the issuances and legal basis as regards to the realization of the said school-based initiative.

It implies that the project is relevant and timely in addressing the issues regarding the maintenance of cleanliness and safety of the school which greatly contribute to building conducive learning environment for all.

It can be seen on the table 3 that the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the implementation of Project GIGO in terms of process gained an overall mean of 3.25 and 3.31 respectively and both verbally interpreted as Much Agree. This indicates that the teachers and students concur with the idea that the process of Project GIGO is followed and carried out properly. However, it can be seen that the lowest mean of both groups is in statement 1 that shows that although there was an orientation which happened, it

was not enough to fully inform all the involved people.

Table 2. Evaluation of the Teachers and Students on the Implementation of Project GIGO in terms of Process

Process	Teachers		Parents	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The project implementer conducted orientation about Project GIGO for the teachers and students.	3.20	Agree	3.21	Much Agree
2. The project implementer formulated audit checklist, policies, and procedures to govern the conduct of activities.	3.30	Much Agree	3.25	Much Agree
3. Internal and stakeholders show positive response regarding the implementation of Project GIGO.	3.23	Agree	3.22	Agree
4. The school has established strong linkages and partnership among stakeholders to aid the project resources.	3.23	Agree	3.24	Agree
5. Everyone plays vital roles as members of the educational community in achieving the shared goals and responsibilities on Project GIGO	3.27	Much Agree	3.37	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.25	Much Agree	3.26	Much Agree

It implies that the involvement of internal and external stakeholders in the implementation is important; thus, they should be aware of all the aspects of Project GIGO.

It can be seen on the table 3 that the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the implementation of Project GIGO in terms of monitoring and evaluation gained an overall mean of 3.42 and 3.33 respectively and both verbally interpreted as Much Agree. This suggests that the teachers and students reach agreement that Project GIGO has effective monitoring and evaluation procedures to assess every phase of its implementation. More so, the results of these evaluations are transpired to the participants making them aware of what is the status of the project.

It implies that monitoring and evaluation is an integral part of every project that should be reflected to the members and clientele to identify the gaps and determine the ways to efficiently address the identified limitations.

Table 3. Evaluation of the Teachers and Students on the Implementation of Project GIGO in terms of Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and Evaluation	Teachers Verbal Interpretation		Parents Verbal Interpretation	
	Mean		Mean	
1. The project has a well-defined monitoring tool that is utilized every quarter to identify the gaps in the implementation.	3.50	Much Agree	3.25	Much Agree
2. The teachers and students are involved in monitoring and evaluation process of Project GIGO.	3.40	Much Agree	3.33	Much Agree
3. The results of the evaluations are presented to the stakeholders to educate everyone about cleanliness and safety of the school environment.	3.30	Much Agree	3.38	Much Agree
4. The project proponent identifies the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats throughout the implementation of the project.	3.43	Much Agree	3.37	Much Agree
5. The project has effective mechanism to monitor and evaluate the project.	3.47	Much Agree	3.31	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.42	Much Agree	3.33	Much Agree

Table 4. Evaluation of the Teachers and Students on the Implementation of Project GIGO in terms of Stakeholder's Participation

Stakeholder's Participation	Teachers Verbal Interpretation		Parents Verbal Interpretation	
	Mean		Mean	
1. The LGU and other private organizations showed full support to the project through cash or in-kind donations.	3.17	Agree	3.14	Agree
2. The members of the school community served as volunteers during the implementation of the project.	3.20	Agree	3.24	Agree
3. The stakeholders participate as advocates of Project GIGO.	3.13	Agree	3.00	Agree
4. The members of the community involved themselves in the school-based and community-based activities related to Project GIGO.	3.23	Agree	3.22	Agree
5. The school and the community establish strong collaboration for the success of Project GIGO.	3.23	Agree	3.23	Agree
Overall Mean	3.19	Agree	3.17	Agree

It can be seen on the table that the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the implementation of Project GIGO in terms of stakeholder's participation gained an overall mean of 3.19 and 3.17 respectively and both verbally interpreted as Agree.

This signifies that the teachers and students recognize the significance of the involvement of the members of the educational community in the success of Project GIGO. On the other hand, it should be noticed that the statements in this criterion all fall in Agree level of evaluation. This is still positive; however, the school should work on how to build linkages from external stakeholders which may greatly enhance the implementation of the project through the support that can be provided by these individuals or groups.

It implies that participation of stakeholders is inevitable in the school initiatives especially those which need strong aids like fund and other sources that would help the implementer achieve the shared goals and responsibilities leading to its success.

Problems encountered by the teachers and students during the implementation of Project GIGO

Problems of the teachers

The following limitations were encountered by the teachers during the conduct of Project GIGO.

- a. The implementation of the project is not intensified.
- b. Teachers do not have enough knowledge as regards the project.
- c. Some parts of the process like monitoring and evaluation were not done during the prescribed time.
- d. Students, parents, and other stakeholders are not aware of the project.
- e. Appreciation activity is not part of the system.

Problems of the students

The following challenges were experienced by the teachers during the conduct of Project GIGO.

- a. Not everyone has the chance to express their thoughts about the project.
- b. There are limitations as regards the trash cans or garbage bins.
- c. There were still some students, specifically speaking, my classmates who are assigned to clean the classroom for the day and view this project GIGO as burdensome.
- d. Segregation bins were labeled but were easily removed as time went by. Students did not participate in putting the labels back together.
- e. Maybe the disobedience of some students in our school.

Suggestions of the teachers and students to further improve the implementation of Project GIGO

The following suggestions were given by the two groups of respondents to further improve the implementation of Project GIGO.

- a. The school shall conduct intensified monitoring. Assign a student or teacher who will be assessing the project every week or month. This way, we can ensure that everyone is following and participating.
- b. Add more big trash bins with labels so that the proper waste management could be followed.
- c. Encourage more stakeholders to support the project because this is a very good and important initiative that is beneficial to all the members of the educational community.
- d. An intensified awareness campaign should be carried out. Every room should be visited and a thorough and comprehensive discussion should be given to all the students and teachers.
- e. Involve the student-leaders in checking the progress of the project on an everyday basis to guarantee its effective implementation.
- f. Monthly meetings of all should be held to report the status of the project, identify the gaps, and provide the solutions.
- g. Simple rewards or recognition could be given to the project supporters.

Conclusion

Based on results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: (1) The students and teachers provided a comprehensive evaluation on the implementation of Project GIGO and concurred to the idea that its objectives, process, monitoring and evaluation, and stakeholders' involvement are evident

during its conduct. (2) There are limitations and gaps that should be addressed by the proponent to achieve the goals of Project GIGO. (3) Students and teachers expressed the possible solutions to the identified problems to further improve the implementation of Project GIGO.

References

- Department of Environment and Natural Resources (2019). Intensified Environmental Protection: Solid Waste Management. Retrieved from <https://www.denr.gov.ph/>
- DepEd Order No. 5, S. 2014 – Implementing Guidelines on the Integration of Gulayan Sa Paaralan, Solid Waste Management and Tree Planting Under the National Greening Program (NGP). Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/>
- Department Order No. 72, S. 2003. Establishment of the Youth for Environment in Schools (YES) Organization. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2003/09/01/do-72-s-2003>
- Llego, M.A. (2019). DepEd Vision, Mission, Mandate, Core Values, and Organization Structure. Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com>.
- Republic of the Philippines, RA 9003. Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. <http://emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/RA-9003.pdf>
- Siedlecki, S. (2020). Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods. *Clinical nurse specialist CNS*. 34. 8-12. 10.1097/NUR.0000000000000493.

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